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Xist functions at three steps in transformation in disease progression in cancer.

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Major functions of Xist included a basic role in transformation (related to DNA damage and repair), in subtype selection (clonal selection, clonal evolution; lineage determination/fate choice in cancer), in metastasis, by promoting tumor survival through heterogeneity at the clonal level.